

Table S1. Summary of species introductions.

Depth is the minimum depth separating the island from a continent or a larger island.

Endemic lists an example of an extant or recently extinct (likely through anthropogenic causes) mammal or bird endemic to the island (with multi-island endemics assigned to the largest island they occur in).

Dataset lists the dataset the species are analysed in and can be either *strict* (where the island contains a true single island endemic, *medium* where there is no strict single island endemics but where the island is the biggest island where at least one species occurs or occurred in, *loose* where the island is big and isolated but lack any endemic species.

Introduced species lists the number of species introduced to the island.

Introduced species predicted to survive lists the number of species with predicted equilibrium sample sizes larger than 1,000. We treat survival under this criterion probabilistically and this will therefore often not be an integer.

Islands are listed within each of the five island regions we use and then listed alphabetically within them

A full list of which species are introduced to which islands can be found in Appendix 1 and a species specific list of references to the introduction of each species on each island can be found in table S2 A few species may be introduced to smaller islands connected to the main islands during the ice ages.

Archipelago	Name	Endemic	Dataset	Introduced species	Introduced species predicted to survive	References ^{d, e, f, g}
Continents						
NA	Africa	<i>Orycteropus afer</i>	Strict	9	9.00	1, 2
NA	Eurasia	<i>Bison bonasus</i>	Strict	10	8.00	1, 3
NA	North America	<i>Canis rufus</i>	Strict	13	13.00	1, 3
NA	South America	<i>Lama guanicoe</i>	Strict	11	11.00	1, 3, 4, 5
NA	Australia	<i>Macropus fuliginosus</i>	Strict	25	25.00	1, 3, 6
Atlantic ocean islands						
Azores	Flores Island	<i>Hydrobates monteiroi</i>	Medium	6	4.03	1, 7
Azores	Pico Island	None	Loose	7	4.08	1, 7
Azores	Sao Jorge Island	None	Loose	6	4.18	1, 7
Azores	Sao Miguel Island	<i>Pyrrhula murina</i>	Strict	10	7.26	1, 7, 8
Azores	Terceira Island	None	Loose	9	5.80	1, 7
Balearic Islands	Ibiza	<i>Rallus eivissensis</i>	Strict	13	9.19	1, 6, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17
Balearic Islands	Mallorca	<i>Eliomys morpheus</i>	Medium	15	13.26	1, 18, 9, 19
Canary and Madeira Islands	El Hiero	None	Loose	6	4.00	1, 7
Canary and Madeira Islands	Fuerteventura	<i>Saxicola dacotiae</i>	Strict	9	7.05	1, 7
Canary and Madeira Islands	Gran Canaria	<i>Canariomys tamarani</i>	Strict	10	8.04	1, 7
Canary and Madeira Islands	La Gomera	None	Loose	7	4.44	1, 7
Canary and Madeira Islands	La Palma	None	Loose	7	4.84	1, 7
Canary and Madeira Islands	Madeira	<i>Columba trocaz</i>	Strict	8	5.30	1, 7
Canary and Madeira Islands	Tenerife	<i>Canariomys bravoi</i>	Strict	10	8.07	1, 7, 8, 20
Cape Verde	Boa Vista	None	Loose	2	0.00	1, 7
Cape Verde	Fogo	None	Loose	4	2.00	1, 7
Cape Verde	Maió	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 7

Cape Verde	Sal	None	Loose	2	0.00	1, 7
Cape Verde	Santiago	<i>Apus alexandri</i>	Medium	6	4.01	1, 7, 8
Cape Verde	Santo Antao	<i>Alauda razae</i>	Medium	2	0.00	1, 7
Cape Verde	Sao Nicolau	None	Loose	2	0.00	1, 7
Cape Verde	Sao Vicente	None	Loose	2	0.00	1, 7
Corsica and Sardinia	Sardinia	<i>Cynotherium sardous</i>	Medium	22	21.98	1, 9, 18
Cyprus	Cyprus	<i>Elephas cypriotes</i>	Strict	11	10.59	1, 6, 18, 21
Greek Islands	Amorgos	None	Loose	4	2.98	1, 22
Greek Islands	Astypalaia	None	Loose	4	3.98	1, 22
Greek Islands	Crete	<i>Candiacervus cretensis</i>	Strict	17	16.45	1, 9, 18, 22
Greek Islands	Karpathos	<i>Elephas tiliensis</i> ^b	Medium	8	7.00	1, 22
Greek Islands	Kythira	None	Loose	10	9.00	1, 22
Greek Islands	Kythnos	None	Loose	4	2.99	1, 22
Greek Islands	Milos	None	Loose	6	5.99	1, 22
Greek Islands	Naxos	None	Loose	9	6.01	1, 22
Greek Islands	Rhodes	None	Loose	16	12.44	1, 22
Greek Islands	Skyros	None	Loose	6	5.00	1, 22

Caribbean islands

Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Andros Island	<i>Icterus northrop</i>	Strict	7	6.38	1, 8, 23
Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Crooked Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 23
Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Great Abaco	None	Loose	2	1.86	1, 8, 23, 24
Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Inagua	<i>Calliphlox lyrura</i>	Medium	3	1.93	1, 23, 8
Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Mayaguana Island	None	Loose	2	2.00	1, 23
Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Middle Caicos	None	Loose	2	2.00	1, 23
Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	San Salvador Island	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 23
Bay and Yucatan Islands	Cozumel	<i>Procyon pygmaeus</i>	Strict	4	2.00	1, 25
Bay and Yucatan Islands	Roatán	<i>Dasyprocta ruatanica</i>	Strict	4	1.22	1, 6, 26, 27, 28
Cuba, Cayman Islands, Jamaica	Cuba	<i>Solenodon cubanus</i>	Strict	21	21.00	1, 23
Cuba, Cayman Islands, Jamaica	Grand Cayman	<i>Turdus ravidus</i>	Strict	6	4.00	1, 23
Cuba, Cayman Islands, Jamaica	Jamaica	<i>Oryzomys antillarum</i>	Strict	9	8.73	1, 8, 23
Hispaniola, Puerto Rico, Virgin Islands	Hispaniola	<i>Acratocnus ye</i>	Strict	11	11.00	1, 8
Hispaniola, Puerto Rico, Virgin Islands	Puerto Rico	<i>Acratocnus odontrigonus</i>	Strict	13	12.53	1, 8
Hispaniola, Puerto Rico, Virgin Islands	Saint Croix	None	Loose	9	5.51	1, 23
Leeward Antilles	Aruba	None	Loose	5	3.00	1, 23
Leeward Antilles	Bonaire	None	Loose	5	2.41	1, 23
Leeward Antilles	Curacao	<i>Oryzomys curasoe</i>	Strict	11	7.19	1, 23
Windward Islands	Antigua	<i>Dendroica subita</i> ^a	Medium	10	5.08	1, 23
Windward Islands	Barbados	<i>Megalomys georginae</i>	Strict	9	6.99	1, 23

Windward Islands	Basse-Terre (Guadeloupe)	<i>Melanerpes herminieri</i>	Strict	10	8.02	1, 23
Windward Islands	Dominica	<i>Amazona arausiaca</i>	Strict	11	8.65	1, 23
Windward Islands	Grenada	<i>Leptotila wellsi</i>	Strict	12	9.77	1, 23
Windward Islands	Marie-Galante	None	Loose	5	2.80	1, 23
Windward Islands	Martinique	<i>Megalomys desmarestii</i>	Strict	8	5.99	1, 8, 23
Windward Islands	Montserrat	<i>Icterus oberi</i>	Strict	2	1.95	1, 23
Windward Islands	Saint Kitts	<i>Pennatomys nivalis</i>	Medium	7	4.76	1, 23
Windward Islands	Saint Lucia	<i>Megalomys luciae</i>	Strict	7	5.00	1, 23
Windward Islands	Saint Vincent (Antilles)	<i>Amazona guildingii</i>	Strict	7	4.98	1, 23
Indian Ocean islands						
Comoro Islands	Anjouan	<i>Myotis anjouanensis</i>	Strict	7	4.23	1, 6, 8, 29
Comoro Islands	Grande Comore	<i>Miniopterus griveaudi</i>	Strict	7	4.55	1, 6, 8, 29, 30, 31
Comoro Islands	Mayotte	<i>Otus mayottensis</i>	Strict	8	5.19	1, 6, 8, 29
Comoro Islands	Moheli	<i>Otus moheliensis</i>	Strict	7	4.05	1, 6, 8, 29
Madagascar	Madagascar	<i>Allocebus trichotis</i>	Strict	7	7.00	1, 32, 33
Mascarene Islands	Mautius	<i>Mormopterus acetabulosus</i>	Strict	11	10.03	1, 32
Mascarene Islands	Reunion	<i>Mormopterus francoismoutoui</i>	Strict	10	8.18	1, 32
Mascarene Islands	Rodrigues	<i>Pteropus rodricensis</i>	Strict	7	4.10	1, 32
Seychelles Granitic	Mahe	<i>Coleura seychellensis</i>	Medium	7	5.94	1, 32
Seychelles Outer islands	Aldabra	<i>Pteropus aldabrensis</i>	Strict	4	2.03	1, 32
Zanzibar Archipelago	Pemba	<i>Pteropus voeltzkowi</i>	Strict	10	9.54	1, 29
Indomalayan islands						
Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Car Nicobar	None	Loose	3	1.00	1, 6
Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Great Nicobar	<i>Crocodyrus nicobarica</i>	Strict	3	2.78	1, 6
Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Kamorta Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 6
Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Katchal island	<i>Pteropus faunulus</i>	Medium	1	1.00	1, 6
Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Middle Andaman	<i>Crocodyrus andamanensis</i>	Strict	11	8.56	1, 34
Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Weh island	None	Loose	3	1.00	1, 6
Christmas Island	Christmas Island	<i>Crocodyrus trichura</i>	Strict	4	2.00	1, 8
Lesser Sunda islands	Alor Island	<i>Otomops johnstonei</i>	Strict	6	4.11	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Atauro Island	None	Loose	2	2.00	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Babar Island	None	Loose	2	2.00	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Damar Island	<i>Ficedula henrici</i>	Strict	2	2.00	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Flores	<i>Homo floresiensis</i>	Strict	8	7.86	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Romang Island	None	Loose	2	2.00	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Rote Island	<i>Rhipidura tenkatei</i>	Medium	4	2.02	1, 6

Lesser Sunda islands	Sangeang	None	Loose	3	3.00	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Savu	None	Loose	4	2.00	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Sermata Island	None	Loose	2	2.00	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Sumba	<i>Ninox rudolfi</i>	Strict	9	8.71	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Sumbawa	None	Loose	6	5.88	1, 6
Lesser Sunda islands	Timor	<i>Rattus timorensis</i>	Strict	10	9.99	1, 6, 35
Lesser Sunda islands	Wetar	<i>Otus tempestatis</i>	Strict	4	4.00	1, 6, 35
Lesser Sunda islands	Yamdena	<i>Melomys cooperae</i>	Strict	5	3.37	1, 6
Philippines	Calayan Island	<i>Gallirallus calayanensis</i>	Strict	3	3.00	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Camiguin	<i>Apomys camiguinensis</i>	Strict	6	3.13	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Camiguin de Babuyan	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Jolo Island	<i>Hypsipetes haynaldi</i>	Medium	4	2.00	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Lubang Island	None	Loose	3	1.00	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Luzon	<i>Abditomys latidens</i>	Strict	10	10.00	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Mindoro	<i>Anonymomys mindorensis</i>	Strict	9	8.59	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Negros	<i>Crocodyrus negrina</i>	Strict	9	8.79	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Palawan	<i>Sundasciurus rabori</i>	Strict	8	7.72	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Sibutu	None	Loose	2	0.00	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Sibuyan	<i>Chrotomys sibuyanensis</i>	Strict	7	3.45	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Siquijor	None	Loose	4	2.00	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Philippines	Tablas Island	<i>Dicrurus menagei</i>	Strict	6	4.00	1, 36, 37, 38 ^h
Ryukyu Islands	Amami Oshima	<i>Tokudaia osimensis</i>	Strict	7	4.45	1, 39, 40
Ryukyu Islands	Iriomote Island	<i>Sittiparus olivaceus</i>	Strict	4	2.44	1, 39
Ryukyu Islands	Miyakojima	<i>Capreolus miyakoensis</i>	Medium	6	3.00	1, 39
Ryukyu Islands	Okinawa Island	<i>Tokudaia muenninki</i>	Strict	9	6.83	1, 39, 41
Ryukyu Islands	Tokunoshima	<i>Tokudaia tokunoshimensis</i>	Strict	6	2.36	1, 39
Sulawesi	Karakelong	<i>Gymnocrex talaudensis</i>	Strict	6	3.24	1, 42, 43
Sulawesi	Pasimaranu	None	Loose	2	2.00	1, 6
Sulawesi	Sangihe	<i>Eutrichomyias rowleyi</i>	Strict	5	3.00	1, 43
Sulawesi	Selayar Island	<i>Symposiachrus everetti</i>	Strict	6	3.35	1, 35
Sulawesi	Siau Island	<i>Tarsius tumpara</i>	Strict	3	1.00	1, 42
Sulawesi	Sulawesi	<i>Tarsius dentatus</i>	Strict	11	11.00	1, 6
Sulawesi	Taliabu	<i>Rattus elaphinus</i>	Medium	3	1.28	1, 6, 42
Sulawesi	Tanah Jampea	<i>Symposiachrus everetti</i>	Strict	4	2.00	1, 6
Sulawesi	Wangi wangi Island	None	Loose	2	2.00	1, 6
Sumatran Islands	Enggano Island	<i>Rattus adustus</i>	Strict	4	2.31	1, 6
Sumatran Islands	Nias	<i>Pteropus melanotus</i>	Medium	5	3.60	1, 6
Sumatran Islands	Siberut	<i>Macaca siberu</i>	Strict	5	3.53	1, 6

Sumatran Islands	Simeulue	<i>Otus umbra</i>	Strict	5	3.01	1, 6
Pacific islands						
Antipodes and Chatham Islands	Chatham Island	<i>Mergus milleneri</i>	Strict	11	8.34	1, 8
Bismarck Archipelago	Dyaul Island	<i>Myiagra cervinicolor</i>	Strict	0	0.00	1, 42
Bismarck Archipelago	Karkar Island	None	Loose	3	0.29	1, 42
Bismarck Archipelago	Lihir Island	None	Loose	2	0.00	1, 42
Bismarck Archipelago	Long Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 42
Bismarck Archipelago	Manus Island	<i>Melomys matambuai</i>	Strict	8	6.04	1, 42
Bismarck Archipelago	Mussau Island	<i>Lalage conjuncta</i>	Strict	4	2.00	1, 42
Bismarck Archipelago	New Britain	<i>Uromys neobritannicus</i>	Strict	7	6.99	1, 42
Bismarck Archipelago	New Ireland	<i>Philemon eichhorni</i>	Strict	9	8.29	1, 42
Bismarck Archipelago	Tatau Island	<i>Erythropitta splendida</i>	Medium	0	0.00	1, 42
Campbell Islands	Campbell Island	<i>Leucocarbo campbelli</i>	Strict	0	0.00	1, 44
Easter Island	Easter Island	<i>Easter Island crane</i> <i>Porzana" sp.</i>	Strict	1	1.00	1, 8
Fiji	Gau Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 45
Fiji	Kadavu Island	<i>Meliphacator</i> <i>provocator</i>	Strict	9	4.64	1, 8, 45
Fiji	Koro Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 45
Fiji	Taveuni Island	<i>Lamprolia victoriae</i>	Strict	6	3.82	1, 8, 45
Fiji	Vanua Levu	<i>Lamprolia klinesmithi</i>	Strict	10	9.03	1, 8, 45
Fiji	Viti Levu	<i>Gymnomyza</i> <i>brunneirostris</i>	Strict	11	10.71	1, 6, 8, 45
Hawaii	Big Island	<i>Viridonia sagittirostris</i>	Strict	11	10.69	1, 8, 46, 47, 48
Hawaii	Kahoolawe	None	Loose	3	2.03	1, 46, 48
Hawaii	Kauai	<i>Chlorodrepanis</i> <i>stejnegeri</i>	Strict	11	8.53	1, 46, 48
Hawaii	Maui	<i>Loxops ochraceus</i>	Strict	14	11.76	1, 46, 48
Hawaii	Niihau	<i>Telespiza ultima</i>	Strict	5	4.05	1, 46, 48
Hawaii	Oahu	<i>Myadestes woahensis</i>	Strict	11	8.97	1, 46, 48
Kosrae and Pohnpei	Kosrae	<i>Pteropus ualanus</i>	Strict	2	2.00	1, 42
Kosrae and Pohnpei	Pohnpei	<i>Aplonis pelzelni</i>	Strict	6	4.00	1, 42
Louisiade Archipelago	Fergusson island	<i>Dactylopsila tatei</i>	Strict	4	1.92	1, 42
Louisiade Archipelago	Misima Island	None	Loose	2	1.07	1, 42
Louisiade Archipelago	Rosell Island	<i>Melomys arcium</i>	Strict	1	1.00	1, 42
Louisiade Archipelago	Sudest Island	<i>Zosterops meeki</i>	Strict	1	1.00	1, 42
Louisiade Archipelago	Woodlark Island	<i>Phalanger lullulae</i>	Medium	2	1.75	1, 42
Macquarie Island	Macquarie Island	<i>Eudyptes schlegeli</i>	Medium	0	0.00	1, 49
Maluku Islands	Buru	<i>Tanygnathus gramineus</i>	Strict	10	9.46	1, 42
Maluku Islands	Gebe Island	<i>Phalanger alexandrae</i>	Strict	4	1.02	1, 42
Maluku Islands	Great Kai Island	<i>Melomys bannisteri</i>	Strict	10	7.35	1, 42

Maluku Islands	Halmahera	<i>Habroptila wallacii</i>	Strict	8	7.94	1, 42
Maluku Islands	Kofiau	<i>Symposiachrus julianae</i>	Strict	0	0.00	1, 42
Maluku Islands	Manipa Island	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 42
Maluku Islands	Obira	<i>Ptilinopus granulifrons</i>	Strict	6	4.16	1, 42
Maluku Islands	Seram	<i>Rhynchomeles prattorum</i>	Strict	11	10.93	1, 42
Maluku Islands	Waigeo	<i>Spilocuscus papuensis</i>	Strict	3	1.31	1, 42
Mariana Islands	Guam	<i>Hypotaenidia owstoni</i>	Strict	11	7.46	1, 8
Mariana Islands	Saipan	<i>Acrocephalus hiwae</i>	Strict	8	5.17	1, 42, 50, 51
Mariana Islands	Tinian	<i>Metabolus takatsukasae</i>	Strict	7	5.00	1, 42, 50
Marquesas	Hiva Oa	<i>Todiramphus godeffroyi</i>	Medium	5	4.00	1, 52
Marquesas	Nuku Hiva	<i>Pomarea nukuhivae</i>	Strict	7	4.80	1, 52
Marquesas	Ua Pou	<i>Pomarea mira</i>	Strict	6	4.00	1, 52
New Caledonia	Grande Terre	<i>Chalinolobus neocaledonicus</i>	Strict	11	10.92	1, 8
New Caledonia	Lifou Island	<i>Miniopterus robustior</i>	Medium	6	4.01	1, 53, 54
New Caledonia	Mare Island	None	Loose	4	1.64	1, 53, 54
New Caledonia	Ouvea Island	<i>Eunymphicus uvaensis</i>	Strict	4	2.06	1, 53, 54
New Hebrides	Ambae	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Ambrym	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Aneityum	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Efate	<i>Mwalau walterlinii</i>	Strict	3	1.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Epi	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Erromango	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Espiritu Santo	<i>Aplonis santovestris</i>	Strict	9	7.53	1, 8, 42
New Hebrides	Gaua	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Maewo	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Nendo	<i>Nyctimene sanctacrucis</i>	Strict	2	1.45	1, 42
New Hebrides	Pentecost Island	None	Loose	2	0.00	1
New Hebrides	Tanna Island	<i>Alopecoenas ferrugineus</i>	Strict	2	0.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Vanikoro	<i>Pteropus tuberculatus</i>	Medium	0	0.00	1, 42
New Hebrides	Vanua Lava	<i>Pteropus fundatus</i>	Strict	0	0.00	1, 42
New Zealand	South Island	<i>Apteryx rowi</i>	Strict	31	31.00	1, 8
Niue and Tonga Islands	Niue	<i>Gallirallus huiatua</i>	Strict	7	4.12	1, 3, 55
Niue and Tonga Islands	Tongatapu	<i>Didunculus placopedetes</i>	Medium	5	3.00	1, 42
Niue and Tonga Islands	Vavau	<i>Pachycephala jacquinoti</i>	Medium	2	0.00	1, 42
Palau Islands	Babelthuap	<i>Caprimulgus phalaena</i>	Strict	5	5.00	1, 3, 42
Samoan Islands	Savai'i	<i>Zosterops samoensis</i>	Strict	6	4.06	1, 8
Samoan Islands	Tutuila	None	Loose	3	1.00	1, 42
Samoan Islands	Upolu	None	Loose	2	0.01	1, 42

Schouten Islands	Biak	<i>Uromys boeadii</i>	Strict	5	3.17	1, 42
Schouten Islands	Numfor	<i>Ceyx mulcatus</i>	Strict	2	1.20	1, 42
Society islands	Moorea	<i>Todiramphus youngi</i>	Strict	5	3.00	1, 56, 57
Society islands	Raiatea	<i>Cyanoramphus ulietanus</i>	Strict	5	3.00	1, 56, 57
Society islands	Tahiti	<i>Todiramphus veneratus</i>	Strict	9	6.83	1, 8, 56, 57
Solomon islands	Bougainville	<i>Stresemannia bougainvillei</i>	Strict	7	6.53	1, 42
Solomon islands	Guadalcanal	<i>Zoothera turipavae</i>	Strict	7	5.95	1, 42
Solomon islands	Malaita	<i>Nyctimene malaitensis</i>	Medium	6	4.50	1, 42
Solomon islands	New Georgia	<i>Pteralopex taki</i>	Medium	5	3.08	1, 42
Solomon islands	Pavuvu Island	None	Loose	3	2.99	1, 42
Solomon islands	Rennell Island	<i>Pteropus rennelli</i>	Strict	2	1.71	1, 42
Solomon islands	San Cristobal	<i>Hipposideros demissus</i>	Strict	6	4.31	1, 42
Solomon islands	Tetepare Island	None	Loose	4	2.00	1, 58
Solomon islands	Vella Lavella	<i>Zosterops vellalavella</i>	Medium	2	2.00	1, 42

Remaining islands

Aleutian Islands	Amchitka Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 59
Aleutian Islands	Atka Island	None	Loose	3	2.08	1, 59
Aleutian Islands	Attu Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 59
Aleutian Islands	Berring Island	None	Loose	5	4.97	1, 60, 61
Aleutian Islands	Chuginadak Island	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 59
Aleutian Islands	Seguam Island	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 59
Aleutian Islands	Semisopochnoi Island	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 59
Aleutian Islands	Yunaska Island	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 59
California Channel Islands	San Clamente island	None	Loose	2	2.00	1, 62
California Channel Islands	Santa Catalina island	None	Loose	6	2.56	1, 62
California Channel Islands	Santa Cruz Island	<i>Aphelocoma insularis</i>	Strict	0	0.00	1, 62
Chiloe Archipelago	Guafo Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 63
Crozet Islands	Ile de l'Est	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 64
Crozet Islands	Possession Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 64
Falkland Islands	East Falkland Island	<i>Dusicyon australis</i>	Medium	12	11.20	1, 65
Galapagos	Floreana Island	<i>Camarhynchus pauper</i>	Strict	5	2.03	1, 66
Galapagos	Isla Isabella	<i>Geospiza heliobates</i>	Strict	8	6.76	1, 66
Galapagos	Isla San Cristobal	<i>Mimus melanotis</i>	Strict	5	2.48	1, 66
Galapagos	Isla Santa Cruz	<i>Megaoryzomys curioi</i>	Strict	8	5.66	1, 66

Galapagos	Marchena Island	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 66
Galapagos	Santiago Island	<i>Nesoryzomys Sp D</i>	Medium	2	2.00	1, 66
Gulf of California Islands	Isla Angel de la Guarda	<i>Peromyscus guardia</i>	Strict	3	2.00	1, 25
Gulf of California Islands	Isla Carmen	None	Loose	3	0.06	1, 25
Gulf of California Islands	Isla Ceralvo	None	Loose	2	0.05	1, 25
Heard and MacDonald Islands	Heard Island	None	Loose	0	0.00	1, 67
Heard and MacDonald Islands	Kerguelen	None	Loose	4	3.78	1, 64
Islas Marias	Isla Maria Madre	<i>Myotis findleyi</i>	Medium	5	2.11	1, 25
Kurile Islands	Atlasov Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 68
Kurile Islands	Iturup	None	Loose	3	1.35	1, 68
Kurile Islands	Onkotan	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 68
Kurile Islands	Shiashkotan	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 68
Kurile Islands	Simushir	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 68
Kurile Islands	Urup	None	Loose	4	1.79	1, 68
Prince Edward Islands	Marion Island	None	Loose	1	1.00	1, 69
Revillagigedos Islands	Socorro Island	<i>Zenaida graysoni</i>	Strict	2	1.00	1, 25
Saint Helena	Saint Helena	<i>Charadrius sanctaehelenae</i>	Strict	6	3.00	1, 65
Sao Tome and Principe	Ilha do Principe	<i>Corythornis nais</i>	Strict	5	3.99	1, 70
Sao Tome and Principe	Sao Tome	<i>Oriolus crassirostris</i>	Strict	9	5.95	1, 70
Sea of Japan	Honshu	<i>Myodes andersoni</i>	Strict	18	18.00	1, 39
Sea of Japan	Okushiri	None	Loose	4	4.00	1, 39
Sea of Japan	Sado Island	<i>Mogera tokudae</i>	Strict	4	1.10	1, 39
Socotra archipleago	Abd al Kuri	<i>Passer hemileucus</i>	Strict	0	0.00	1
Socotra archipleago	Socotra	<i>Emberiza socotrana</i>	Strict	6	5.27	1, 6
South Georgia Islands	South Georgia Island	<i>Anthus antarcticus</i>	Medium	1	1.00	1, 8
West Baja California Islands	Isla Guadalupe	<i>Junco insularis</i>	Strict	2	1.00	1, 25

Notes

a Species is actually endemic to Barbuda but that island is connected to Antigua during ice ages

b Species is actually endemic to Tilos but that island is connected to Karpathos during ice ages

c Species is actually endemic to Rábida but that island is connected to Karpathos during ice ages

d Dogs and cats assumed present for any island with at least 10,000 people

e Feral pigs are treated differently between sources. For consistency, we therefore only scored them as introduced if they are listed as such in [1] unless other sources explicitly note the feral nature of pigs on the island

f All island populations of *Mus musculus* marked as origin uncertain by IUCN assumed to be introduced

g Historic range of *Rattus exulans* set as lesser Sunda islands following [71]. All populations outside this area treated as introduced.

h *Paradoxurus hermaphroditus* and *Viverra zangalunga* assumed to be introduced to the Philippines. There is very strong genetic differentiation other parts of the range for both species [72, 73] but clear evidence of recent gene flow between Borneo and the Philippines in both which seems highly implausible.

References

- 1) Long, J.L. (2003) *Introduced Mammals of the World: their History, Distribution and Influence*. CSIRO Publishing.
- 2) Lalis, A., Leblois, R., Liefried, S., Ouarour, A. Beeravolu, C.R. Michaux, J., Hamani, A., Denys, C. & Nicolas, V. (2015) New molecular data favour an anthropogenic introduction of the wood mouse (*Apodemus sylvaticus*) in North Africa. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research.*, 54, 4–12.
- 3) CABI Invasive species compendium (2020) <http://www.cabi.org/publishing-products/invasive-species-compendium/>
- 4) Dembitzer, J. (2017) The case for hippos in Colombia. *Israel Journal of Ecology and Evolution*, 63, 5–8.
- 5) Willner, G.R., Feldhamer, G., Zucker, E.E., Chapman, J.A. (1980) *Ondatra zibethicus*. *Mammalian Species*, 141, 1–8.
- 6) IUCN (2021) The IUCN Red List of threatened species. Version 2021-1 <https://www.iucnredlist.org>.
- 7) Masseti, M. (2010) Mammals of the Macaronesian islands (the Azores, Madeira, the Canary and Cape Verde islands): redefinition of the ecological equilibrium. *Mammalia*, 74, 3–34.
- 8) Longman, E.K., Rosenblad, K. & Sax D.F. (2018) Extreme homogenization: The past, present and future of mammal assemblages on islands. *Global Ecology & Biogeography*, 27, 77–95.
- 9) Dubey, S., Cosson, J.F., Magnanou, E., Vohralik, V., Benda, P., Frynta, D., Hutterer, R., Vogel, V. & Vogel P. (2007) Mediterranean populations of the Lesser white-toothed shrew (*Crocidura suaveolens* group): an unexpected puzzle of Pleistocene survivors and prehistoric introductions. *Molecular Ecology*, 16, 3438–3452.
- 10) Renaud, S. & Michaux J.R. (2007) Mandibles and molars of the wood mouse, *Apodemus sylvaticus* (L.): Integrated latitudinal pattern and mosaic insular evolution. *Journal of Biogeography*, 34, 339–355.

- 11) Clevenger A.P. (1995) Seasonality and relationships of food resource use of *Martes martes*, *Genetta genetta* and *Felis catus* in the Balearic Islands. *Revue D'Ecologie*, 50, 109–131.
- 12) Tattersall, F.H. Nowell, F. & Smith R.H. (1994) A review of the endoparasites of wild House Mice *Mus domesticus*. *Mammal Review*, 24, 61–71.
- 13) Rodrigues, M., Bos, A.R., Schembri, P.J., de Lima, R.F., Lymberakis, P., Parpal, ..., Fernandes, C. (2017) Origin and introduction history of the least weasel (*Mustela nivalis*) on Mediterranean and Atlantic islands inferred from genetic data. *Biological Invasions*, 19, 399–421.
- 14) Millán, J., Casáis, R., Delibes-Mateos, M., Calvete, C., Rouco, C., Castro, F., ... Villafuerte R. (2012) et al. Widespread exposure to *Sarcoptes scabiei* in wild European rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) in Spain. *Veterinary Parasitology*, 183, 323–329.
- 15) Genovesi, P. & Carnevali L. (2011) Invasive alien species on European islands: eradications and priorities for future work on Island invasives. In .R. Veitch, M.N. Clout, & D.R. Towns, (Eds) *Island Invasives: Eradication and Management* (pp. 56-62) IUCN Publications.
- 16) Sommer, R., Zoller, H., Kock, D., Böhme, W. & Griseau A. (2005) Feeding of the barn owl, *Tyto alba* with first record of the European free-tailed bat, *Tadarida teniotis* on the island of Ibiza (Spain, Balearics). *Folia Zoologica*, 54, 364–370.
- 17) Kirwan D. (2020) Return of the Es Vedra goats <https://www.dannykayibiza.com/return-of-the-es-vedra-goats>.
- 18) Vigne J.D. (1999) The large “true” Mediterranean islands as a model for the Holocene human impact on the European vertebrate fauna? In N. Benneke (Eds.) *The Holocene History of the European Vertebrate Fauna* (pp- 295-322). Deutsches Archäologisches Institut, Eurasien-Abteilung.
- 19) Reumer, J.W.F. & Sanders E.A.C. (1984) Changes in the vertebrate fauna of Menorca in prehistoric and classical times. *Zeitschrift für Säugetierkunde*, 49, 321–325.
- 20) Garzon-Machado, V., del-Arco-Aguilar, M.J. & Perez-de-Paz, P.L. (2012) Threat or threatened species? A paradox in conservation biology. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 20, 228–230.

- 21) Hadjisterkotis, E. (2004) The introduction of wild boar *Sus scrofa* in Cyprus: an alien species in a highly endemic area. *Galemys*, 16, 233–242.
- 22) Masseti M. (2012) *Atlas of terrestrial mammals of the Ionian and Aegean islands* Walter de Gruyter.
- 23) Borroto-Páez, R. & Woods C.A. (2012) *Status and impact of introduced mammals in the West Indies Terrestrial mammals of the West Indies*: Florida Museum of Natural History and Wacahoota Press.
- 24) Rolling Harbour Abaco (2016) Abaco Barbs – Endangered wild horses
<https://rollingharbour.com/birds-etc/abaco-barbs-the-islands-endangered-wild-horses/>
- 25) Aguirre-muñoz, A., Samaniego-Herrera, A., Luna-Mendoza, L., Ortiz-Alcaraz, A., Rodríguez-Malagón, M. Méndez-Sánchez, F., ... Robles, M. L. (2011) Island restoration in Mexico: ecological outcomes after systematic eradications of invasive mammals In Veitch, C.R., Clout, M.N. & Towns, D.R. (Eds.) *Island Invasives: Eradication and Management* (pp. 250-258). IUCN Publications.
- 26) Bermingham, E., Coates, A.G., Cruz, D.G., Emmons, L., Foster, R.B., Leschen, R., ..., & Werfel B. (1998) Geology and terrestrial flora and fauna of Cayos Cochinos, Honduras. *Revista de Biología Tropical*. 46, 15–37.
- 27) Lee, T.E., Hartline, H.B. & Barnes, B M. (2006) *Dasyprocta ruatanica*. *Mammalian Species*, 800, 1–3.
- 28) Tourismroatan Roatan Wildlife and Nature (2020) <http://tourismroatan.com/things-to-do/wildlife-and-nature>.
- 29) Walsh, M.T. (2009) Island subsistence: hunting, trapping and the translocation of wildlife in the Western Indian Ocean Azania. *Archaeological Research in Africa*, 42, 83–113.
- 30) Cheke, A. (2010) The timing of arrival of humans and their commensal animals on Western Indian Ocean oceanic islands. *Phelsuma*, 18, 38–69.
- 31) Hawlitschek, O., Brückman, B., Berger, J., Green, K. & Glaw, F. (2011) Integrating field surveys and remote sensing data to study distribution, habitat use and conservation status of the herpetofauna of the Comoro Islands. *ZooKeys*, 144, 21–78.

- 32) Russell, J.C., Cole, N.C., Zuël, N. & Rocomora, G. (2016) Introduced mammals on Western Indian Ocean islands. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 6, 132–144.
- 33) Goodman, S.M. (1995) *Rattus* on Madagascar and the dilemma of protecting the endemic rodent fauna. *Conservation Biology*, 9, 450–453.
- 34) Rauf A. (2010) “Invasives and their impact on Andaman biodiversity. In Ramakrishna, Raghunathan, C. & Sivaperuman, C (Eds.) *Recent Trends in Biodiversity of Andaman and Nicobar Islands* (pp. 511–517). Zoological Survey of India.
- 35) Heinsohn, T.E. (2002) Status of the common spotted cuscus *Spilocuscus maculatus* and other wild mammals on Selayar Island, Indonesia, with notes on Quaternary faunal turnover. *Australian Mammalogy*, 24, 199–208.
- 36) Heaney, L R. (1986) Biogeography of mammals in SE Asia: estimates of rates of colonization, extinction and speciation. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 28, 127–165.
- 37) Joshi , R. C.(2006) “Invasive alien species (IAS): concerns and status in the Philippines” In: *Proceedings of the International Workshop on the Development of Database (APASD) for Biological Invasion., Taiwan Agricultural Chemicals and Toxic Substance Research Institute* (pp. 1-23).
- 38) Heaney, L.R., Dolar, M.L., Balete, D.S., Esselstyn, J.A., Rickart, E.A., & Sedlock, J.L. (2010) Synopsis of Philippine mammals
http://archive.fieldmuseum.org/philippine_mammals
- 39) National Institute of Environmental Studies, Japan Invasive species of Japan (2020)
https://www.nies.go.jp/biodiversity/invasive/DB/aetoc1_mammals.html
- 40) Watari, Y., Takatsuki, S. & Miyashita T. (2008) Effects of exotic mongoose (*Herpestes javanicus*) on the native fauna of Amami-Oshima Island, southern Japan, estimated by distribution patterns along the historical gradient of mongoose invasion. *Biological Invasions*, 10, 7–17.
- 41) Ogura, G., Sasaki, T., Toyama, M., Takehara, K., Nakachi, M., Ishibashi, O., Kawashima, Y. & Oda, S. (2002) Food habits of the feral small Asian Mongoose (*Herpestes javanicus*) and impacts on native species in the northern part of Okinawa Island. *Honyurui Kagaku. Mammalian Science*, 42, 53–62.

- 42) Flannery, T. (1995) *Mammals of the South-West Pacific and Moluccan Islands*. Cornell University Press.
- 43) Riley, J. (2002) Mammals on the Sangihe and Talaud Islands, Indonesia, and the impact of hunting and habitat loss. *Oryx* 36, 288–296,
- 44) McClelland P.J. (2011) Campbell Island – pushing the boundaries of rat eradications. In Veitch, C.R. Clout, M.N. & Towns, D.R. (Eds.) *Island Invasives: Eradication and Management* (pp. 204-207). IUCN Publications.
- 45) Pernetta, J.C. & Watling D. (1978) The introduced and native terrestrial vertebrates of Fiji. *Pacific Science*, 32, 223–244.
- 46) HEAR. (2020) Hawaiian Ecosystems at Risk project (HEAR) Invasive species information for Hawaii and the Pacific. www.hear.org
- 47) Daily Mail (2016) Last of Hawaii's 500 wild donkeys which once roamed freely and wreaked havoc on the Big Island prepare to be adopted into new homes www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-3600357/The-Hawaiis-wild-donkeys-prepped-adoption.html
- 48) Wildlife of Hawaii (2021) <https://wildlifeofhawaii.com/hawaii-mammals.html>
- 49) ABC (2017) Macquarie Island declared pest free after 7-year eradication program <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2014-04-07/macquarie-island-declared-pest-free-after-eradication-program/5373336>
- 50) Wiles, G.J., Amerson, A.B., Beck R.E. (1990) The mammals of Tinian, Mariana Islands. *Micronesica*, 23, 167–180.
- 51) Stinson D.W. (1994) Birds and mammals recorded from the Mariana Islands In Asakura, A. & Furuki T. (Eds.) *Biological Expedition to the Northern Mariana Islands, Micronesia. Natural History Research, Special Issue No. 1* (pp. 333–344) Natural History Museum and Institute, Chiba, Japan.
- 52) Soubeyran Y. (2008) Espèces exotiques envahissantes dans les collectivités françaises d’outre-mer. Etat des lieux et recommandations Collection Planète Nature. Comité français de l’UICN. IUCN.

- 53) Sherley G. (2000) *Invasive species in the Pacific: a technical review and draft regional strategy*. Graphic Press & Packaging Ltd.
- 54) Beauvais, M.L., Coléno, A. & Jourdan H. (2006) *Invasive species in the New Caledonian archipelago: A major economic and environmental hazard* Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, Marseille.
- 55) Powlesland, R., Butler, J.D. & Westbrooke I. (2010) Was tropical cyclone Heta or hunting by people responsible for decline of the Lupe (*Ducula pacifica*) (Aves: Columbidae) population on Niue during 1994–2004? *Pacific Science*, 62, 461–471.
- 56) Meyer, J.Y. & Butaud J.F. (2009) The impacts of rats on the endangered native flora of French Polynesia (Pacific Islands): drivers of plant extinction or coup de grâce species? *Biological Invasions*, 11, 1569–1585.
- 57) Giovas C.M. (2006) No pig atoll: Island biogeography and the extirpation of a Polynesian domesticate. *Asian Perspectives*, 45, 69–95.
- 58) Read, J. L., Moseby, K. (2006): Vertebrates of Tetepare Island, Solomon Islands. *Pacific Science* 60, 69–79.
- 59) Gotthardt, T., Kenney, L., Greenstein, C. & Reimer, J. (2015) A Synthesis and Vulnerability Assessment of Terrestrial Invasive Species in the Aleutian and Bering Sea Islands. Prepared for the Aleutian and Bering Sea Islands LCC. Alaska Center for Conservation Science, University of Alaska Anchorage
- 60) State Natural Biosphere Reserve "Komandorskiy" (2021) <http://komandorsky.ru/en/the-largest-deer-herd-found-on-bering-island.html>
- 61) Barabash-Nikiforov I (1938) Mammals of the Commander Islands and the Surrounding Sea. *Journal of Mammalogy* 19, 423-429.
- 62) Knowlton, J. L., Donlan, C. J., Roemer, G. W., Samaniego-Herrera, A., Keitt, B. S., Wood, B., . . . , Tershy, B. R. (2007) Eradication of non-native mammals and the status of insular mammals on the California Channel Islands, USA, and Pacific Baja California Peninsula Islands, Mexico. *Southwestern Naturalist*, 52, 528-540.

- 63) Moreno-Gómez F., Reyes-Arriagada R. & Schlatter R. P. (2010) Introduced rats on Guafo Island, Chile and their potential impact on sooty shearwater *Puffinus griseus* (Gmelin 1789). *Aliens* 29, 34–3.
- 64) Chapui, J., Bousses, P., & Barnaud, G. (1994). Alien mammals, impact and management in the French Sub Antarctic Islands. *Biological Conservation*, 67, 97–104.
- 65) Varnham, K. (2006) Non-native species in UK overseas territories: a review. *Joint Nature Conservation Committee Report*, 372, 1–35.
- 66) Phillips, R.B., Wiedenfeld, D.A. & Snell H.L. (2012) Current status of alien vertebrates in the Galapagos Islands: invasion history, distribution, and potential impacts. *Biological Invasions*, 14, 461–480.
- 67) Australian Antarctic Division (2020) <http://heardisland.antarctica.gov.au/nature/animals-of-himi/introduced-species>.
- 68) Litvinenko, N. M. (1993). Effects of disturbance by people and introduced predators on seabirds in the northwest Pacific. In: K. Vermeer, K. T. Briggs, K. H. Morgan, & D. Siegel-Causey, *The status, ecology, and conservation of marine birds of the North Pacific* (pp. 227–231). Canadian Wildlife Service.
- 69) de Bruyn, P. J. N. (2017) Hard but worth it: researchers fight invasives on Subantarctic islands (commentary) <https://news.mongabay.com/2017/06/hard-but-worth-it-researchers-fight-invasives-on-subantarctic-islands-commentary/>
- 70) Dutton J.(1994) Introduced mammals in Sao Tome and Principe: possible threats to biodiversity. *Biodiversity & Conservation*, 3, 927–938.
- 71) Thomson, V., Aplin, K.P., Cooper, A., Hisheh, S., Suzuki, H., Maryanto, I., Yap, G., Donnellan S.C. (2014) Molecular genetic evidence for the place of origin of the Pacific Rat *Rattus exulans*. *PLoS One*, 9. e91356.
- 72) Veron, G., Patau, M.L., Toth, M., Goonatilake, M. & Jennings A.P.(2014) How many species of *Paradoxurus* civets are there? New insights from India and Sri Lanka. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research*, 53, 161–174.

73) Veron, G., Willsch, M., Dacosta, V., Patou, M.L., Seymour, A., Bonillo, C., ..., Wilting, A. (2014) The distribution of the Malay civet *Viverra zibethica* (Carnivora: Viverridae) across Southeast Asia: Natural or human-mediated dispersal? *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 170, 917–932.

Table S2. Individual references to specific introductions

Order	Family	Specis	Source	Note
Continents		Africa		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela putorius</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Hemitragus jemlahicus</i>	1	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	1	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Echimyidae	<i>Myocastor coypus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>	2	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Sciurus carolinensis</i>	1	
Continents		Eurasia		
Carnivora	Carnivora	<i>Martes melampus</i>	1	
Carnivora	Carnivora	<i>Neovison vison</i>	1	
Carnivora	Carnivora	<i>Procyon lotor</i>	1	
Eulipotyphla	Eulipotyphla	<i>Atelerix algirus</i>	1	
Lagomorpha	Lagomorpha	<i>Sylvilagus floridanus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Rodentia	<i>Castor canadensis</i>	1	
Rodentia	Rodentia	<i>Ondatra zibethicus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Rodentia	<i>Myocastor coypus</i>	1	
Continents		North America		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Hemitragus jemlahicus</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Axis axis</i>	3	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Cervus nippon</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Dama dama</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa unicolor</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	1	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Echimyidae	<i>Myocastor coypus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	1	
Continents		South America		
		<i>Herpestes</i>	1	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bubalus arnee</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Axis axis</i>	3	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Cervus elaphus</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Dama dama</i>	1	
		<i>Hippopotamus</i>	4	
Cetartiodactyla	Hippopotamidae	<i>amphibius</i>		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Castoridae	<i>Castor canadensis</i>	1	
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Callosciurus erythraeus</i>	3	
Continents		Australia		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	6	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos javanicus</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bubalus arnee</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Camelidae	<i>Camelus dromedarius</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Axis axis</i>	3	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Cervus elaphus</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Dama dama</i>	1	

Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa unicorn</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura maxi</i>	1	Introduced to Aru island which are connected to austrlia during ice ages
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	1	Introduced to New Guinea which is connected during ica ages
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	1	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	6	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	1	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	1	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Macaca fascicularis</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	1	Introduced to New Guinea which is connected during ica ages
<hr/>				
Atlantic Ocean islands	Azores	Flores Island		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela putorius</i>	7	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Cervus elaphus</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
<hr/>				
Atlantic Ocean islands	Azores	Pico Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela putorius</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
<hr/>				
Atlantic Ocean islands	Azores	Sao Jorge Island		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela putorius</i>	7	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Cervus elaphus</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
<hr/>				
Atlantic Ocean islands	Azores	Sao Miguel Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela nivalis</i>	7	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela putorius</i>	7	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	7	Present in Santa Maria (connected in ice ages)
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus europaeus</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
<hr/>				
Atlantic Ocean islands	Azores	Terceira Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela nivalis</i>	7	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela putorius</i>	7	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus europaeus</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
<hr/>				
Atlantic Ocean islands	Balearic Islands	Ibiza		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes martes</i>	11	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela nivalis</i>	13	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Genetta genetta</i>	11	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	17	Present in Es Vedra (connected in ice ages)
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Atelerix algirus</i>	6	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura russula</i>	9	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	14	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>	10	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	12	

			11, 15	11) Only lists "Rattus sp" but refer to Rattus rattus in study on another island with only one rat species present. 15) gives evidence of former presence of R. norvegicus in nearby islet
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	11	See above
Atlantic Ocean islands	Balearic Islands	Mallorca		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes martes</i>	18	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela nivalis</i>	18	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Genetta genetta</i>	18	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	18	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Atelerix algirus</i>	18	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura suaveolens</i>	9	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus granatensis</i>	18	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Gliridae	<i>Eliomys quercinus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	18	
	Canary and Madeira			
Atlantic Ocean islands	Islands	El Hiero		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
	Canary and Madeira	Fuerteventura		
Atlantic Ocean islands	Islands			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	7	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Atelerix algirus</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Atlantoxerus getulus</i>	7	
	Canary and Madeira	Gran Canaria		
Atlantic Ocean islands	Islands			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	7	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Atelerix algirus</i>	7	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura russula</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Atlantoxerus getulus</i>	7	
	Canary and Madeira	La Gomera		
Atlantic Ocean islands	Islands			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Cervus elaphus</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
	Canary and Madeira	La Palma		
Atlantic Ocean islands	Islands			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ammotragus lervia</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	

Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Canary and Madeira Islands	Madeira		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela putorius</i>	7	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Canary and Madeira Islands	Tenerife		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ammotragus lervia</i>	20	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	7	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Atelerix algirus</i>	7	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus etruscus</i>	7	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Cape Verde	Boa Vista		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Atlantic Ocean islands	Cape Verde	Fogo		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
	Cercopithecidae	<i>Chlorocebus pygerythrus</i>	7	
Primates		<i>pygerythrus</i>		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Cape Verde	Sal		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Atlantic Ocean islands	Cape Verde	Santiago		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
	Cercopithecidae	<i>Chlorocebus pygerythrus</i>	7	
Primates		<i>pygerythrus</i>		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	7	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	8	Record only given by archipelago but assigned to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	7	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Cape Verde	Santo Antao		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Atlantic Ocean islands	Cape Verde	Sao Nicolau		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Atlantic Ocean islands	Cape Verde	Sao Vicente		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Atlantic Ocean islands	Corsica and Sardinia	Sardinia		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	18	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	18	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes martes</i>	18	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela nivalis</i>	18	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela putorius</i>	18	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	18	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Cervus elaphus</i>	18	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Dama dama</i>	18	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	18	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus europaeus</i>	18	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura russula</i>	18	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura suaveolens</i>	9	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus etruscus</i>	18	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus capensis</i>	18	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Gliridae	<i>Eliomys quercinus</i>	18	

Rodentia	Gliridae	<i>Glis glis</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	18	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Cyprus	Cyprus		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	18	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	18	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	18	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Hemiechinus auritus</i>	18	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus etruscus</i>	18	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus capensis</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	18	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	18	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Greek islands	Amorgos		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes foina</i>	22	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	22	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	22	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Greek islands	Astypalaia		
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	22	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	22	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	22	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Greek islands	Crete		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes foina</i>	22	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Meles meles</i>	22	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela nivalis</i>	22	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	22	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Dama dama</i>	22	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22	
			22	Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura suaveolens</i>		
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus etruscus</i>	22	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	22	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	22	
			22	Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus mystacinus</i>		
			22	Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	22	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	22	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	22	
Atlantic Ocean islands	Greek islands	Karpathos		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes foina</i>	22	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22	
			22	Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura leucodon</i>		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	22	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	22	
			22	Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	22	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	22	
		<i>Kythira</i>		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes foina</i>	22	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22	
			22	Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura suaveolens</i>		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	22	

Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	22		
			22		Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus mystacinus</i>			Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
			22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>			
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	22		
Atlantic Ocean islands	Greek islands	Kythnos			
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes foina</i>	22		
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	22		
Atlantic Ocean islands	Greek islands	Milos			
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22		
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus etruscus</i>	22		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	22		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	22		
Atlantic Ocean islands	Greek islands	Naxos			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes foina</i>	22		
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22		Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
			22		
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crociodura suaveolens</i>			
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	22		Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
			22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus mystacinus</i>			Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
			22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>			
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	22		
Atlantic Ocean islands	Greek islands	Rhodes			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a	
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	22		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a	
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes foina</i>	22		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Meles meles</i>	22		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Dama dama</i>	22		
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22		Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
			22		
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crociodura suaveolens</i>			
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus etruscus</i>	22		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	22		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	22		Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
			22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus mystacinus</i>			Source only lists presence and not status. Genus is native in archipelago but we judge this as introduced
			22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>			
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	22		
Atlantic Ocean islands	Greek islands	Skyros			
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes foina</i>	22		
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus roumanicus</i>	22		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	22		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	22		
Caribbean islands	Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Andros Island			

Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	8	Only listed as Bahamas. Assigned here to biggest island
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	8	Only listed as Bahamas. Assigned here to biggest island
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	8	Only listed as Bahamas. Assigned here to biggest island
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	23	Only listed as Bahamas. Assigned here to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	Only listed as Bahamas. Assigned here to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	Only listed as Bahamas. Assigned here to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	Only listed as Bahamas. Assigned here to biggest island
Caribbean islands	Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Crooked Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Great Abaco		
Carnivora	Procyonidae	<i>Procyon lotor</i>	23	Present in Grand Bahama (connected in ice ages)
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Inagua		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	23	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	23	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Mayaguana		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Bahamas and Turks and Caicos	Middle Caicos		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Bay and Yucatan Islands	Cozumel		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	25	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	9	
Caribbean islands	Bay and Yucatan Islands	Roatan		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	28	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	27	
Caribbean islands	Cuba, Cayman Islands, Jamaica	Cuba		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>Herpestes auropunctatus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Boselaphus tragocamelus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bubalus arnee</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Tragelaphus derbianus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	23	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	23	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	23	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	23	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Chlorocebus aethiops</i>	23	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Macaca arctoides</i>	23	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Macaca fascicularis</i>	23	
Rodentia	Cuniculidae	<i>Cuniculus paca</i>	23	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta mexicana</i>	23	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta punctata</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	

	Cuba, Cayman Islands,	Grand Cayman		
Caribbean islands	Jamaica			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta punctata</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
	Cuba, Cayman Islands,	Jamaica		
Caribbean islands	Jamaica			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	8	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	8	
	Hispaniola, Puerto	Hispaniola		
Caribbean islands	Rico, Virgin Islands			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	8	
	Hispaniola, Puerto	Puerto Rico		
Caribbean islands	Rico, Virgin Islands			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	8	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	8	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	8	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Erythrocebus patas</i>	8	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Macaca mulatta</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	8	
	Hispaniola, Puerto	Saint Croix		
Caribbean islands	Rico, Virgin Islands			
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	23	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	23	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
	Leeward Antilles	Aruba		
Caribbean islands				
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Sylvilagus floridanus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	

Caribbean islands	Leeward Antilles	Bonaire		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Leeward Antilles	Curacao		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	23	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Sylvilagus floridanus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Antigua		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Dama dama</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	23	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Barbados		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	23	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	23	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Chlorocebus aethiops</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Basse Terre		
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Guadeloupe		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Carnivora	Procyonidae	<i>Procyon lotor</i>	23	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	23	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Dominica		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	23	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	23	
Didelphimorphia	Didelphidae	<i>Didelphis marsupialis</i>	23	
Didelphimorphia	Didelphidae	<i>Marmosa robinsoni</i>	23	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Grenada		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a

		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	23	
Didelphimorphia	Didelphidae	<i>Didelphis marsupialis</i>	23	
Didelphimorphia	Didelphidae	<i>Marmosa robinsoni</i>	23	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Cercopithecus mona</i>	23	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Chlorocebus aethiops</i>	23	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
<hr/>				
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Marie-Galente		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
<hr/>				
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Martinique		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Carnivora	Procyonidae	<i>Procyon lotor</i>	8	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
<hr/>				
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Montserrat		
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
<hr/>				
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Saint Kitts		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Chlorocebus aethiops</i>	23	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
<hr/>				
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Saint Lucia		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Didelphimorphia	Didelphidae	<i>Didelphis marsupialis</i>	23	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
<hr/>				
Caribbean islands	Windward Islands	Saint Vincent		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	23	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Didelphimorphia	Didelphidae	<i>Didelphis marsupialis</i>	23	
Rodentia	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta leporina</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	23	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	23	
<hr/>				
Indian ocean islands	Comoro Islands	Anjouan		
Afrosoricida	Tenrecidae	<i>Tenrec ecaudatus</i>	32	
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverricula indica</i>	32	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	32	
Primates	Lemuridae	<i>Eulemur mongoz</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	
<hr/>				
Indian ocean islands	Comoro Islands	Grande Comore		
Afrosoricida	Tenrecidae	<i>Tenrec ecaudatus</i>	32	
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	32	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>Herpestes javanicus</i>	32	

Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverricula indica</i>	32	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	
Indian ocean islands	Comoro Islands	Mayotte		
Afrosoricida	Tenrecidae	<i>Tenrec ecaudatus</i>	32	
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	32	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverricula indica</i>	32	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	32	
Primates	Lemuridae	<i>Eulemur fulvus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	32	
Indian ocean islands	Comoro Islands	Moheli		
Afrosoricida	Tenrecidae	<i>Tenrec ecaudatus</i>	32	
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	32	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverricula indica</i>	32	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	32	
Primates	Lemuridae	<i>Eulemur mongoz</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	
Indian ocean islands	Madagascar	Madagascar		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverricula indica</i>	32	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Potamochoerus porcus</i>	32	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	32	
Indian ocean islands	Mascarene islands	Mauitius		
Afrosoricida	Tenrecidae	<i>Tenrec ecaudatus</i>	32	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	32	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>Herpestes fuscus</i>	32	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	32	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	32	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus nigricollis</i>	32	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Macaca fascicularis</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	32	
Indian ocean islands	Mascarene islands	Reunion		
Afrosoricida	Tenrecidae	<i>Tenrec ecaudatus</i>	32	
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	32	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	32	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	32	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	32	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	32	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus nigricollis</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	32	
Indian ocean islands	Mascarene islands	Rodrigues		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	32	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	32	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	32	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	32	
Indian ocean islands	Seychelles Granitic	Mahe		
Afrosoricida	Tenrecidae	<i>Tenrec ecaudatus</i>	32	Source lists introduction to Granitic Seychelles
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	32	Source lists introduction to Granitic Seychelles
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus nigricollis</i>	32	Source lists introduction to Granitic Seychelles
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	32	Source lists introduction to Granitic Seychelles
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	Source lists introduction to Granitic Seychelles

Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	32	Source lists introduction to Granitic Seychelles
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	32	Source lists introduction to Granitic Seychelles
Indian ocean islands	Seychelles Outer islands	Aldabra		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	5	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	32	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	32	
Indian ocean islands	Zanzibar Archipelago	Pemba		
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverricula indica</i>	29	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Philantomba monticola</i>	29	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura fuscomurina</i>	29	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	29	
Hyracoidea	Procaviidae	<i>Dendrohyrax validus</i>	29	
		<i>Chlorocebus</i>	29	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>pygerythrus</i>		
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Ptilocolobus kirkii</i>	29	
Primates	Galagidae	<i>Otolemur garnettii</i>	29	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	29	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	29	
Indomalayan islands	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Car Nicobar		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Great Nicobar		
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Kamorta Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Katchal Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	1	
Indomalayan islands	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Middle Andaman		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bubalus arnee</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Axis axis</i>	34	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Muntiacus muntjak</i>	34	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Proboscidea	Elephantidae	<i>Elephas maximus</i>	34	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	34	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	34	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	34	
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Funambulus palmarum</i>	34	
Indomalayan islands	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	Weh		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	1	
Indomalayan islands	Christmas Island	Christmas Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	8	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	8	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Alor Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Atauro Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	

Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Babar Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Damar Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Flores		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Romand Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Rote Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Sangeang		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Savu		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Sermata Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Sumba		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	6	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Sumbawa		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Timor		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	6	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	35	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Wetar		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	35	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Lesser Sunda islands	Yamdena		

Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Camiguin		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	38	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Calayan Island		
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Camiguin de Babuyanes		
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Jolo Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Lubang Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Luzon		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	38	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverra tangalunga</i>	38	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Mindoro		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	38	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverra tangalunga</i>	38	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Negros		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	38	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverra tangalunga</i>	38	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Palawan		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	38	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverra tangalunga</i>	38	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	38	

Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tiomanicus</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Sibutu		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Sibuyan		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	38	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverra tangalunga</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Siquijor		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Philippines	Tablas Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	38	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	38	
Indomalayan islands	Ryukyu Islands	Amami Oshima		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	40	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela itatsi</i>	39	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	40	
Indomalayan islands	Ryukyu Islands	Iriomote Island		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	39	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	39	
Indomalayan islands	Ryukyu Islands	Miyakojima		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela itatsi</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	39	
Indomalayan islands	Ryukyu Islands	Okinawa Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	39	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela itatsi</i>	39	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	39	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	39	
Indomalayan islands	Ryukyu Islands	Tokunoshima		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela itatsi</i>	39	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	39	
Indomalayan islands	Sulawesi	Karakelong		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos javanicus</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	43	

Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	43	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	43	
Indomalayan islands	Sulawesi	Pasimarannu		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Sulawesi	Sangihe		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	43	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	43	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	43	
Indomalayan islands	Sulawesi	Selayar Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	35	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	35	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Spilocuscus maculatus</i>	35	
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Callosciurus notatus</i>	35	
Indomalayan islands	Sulawesi	Siau Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	43	
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Indomalayan islands	Sulawesi	Sulawesi		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	6	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverra tangalunga</i>	6	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	6	
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Callosciurus prevostii</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Sulawesi	Taliabu		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Sulawesi	Tanah Jamepa		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Sulawesi	Wangi wangi Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Sumatran Islands	Enggano Island		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos javanicus</i>	1	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Sumatran Islands	Nias		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Sumatran Islands	Siberut		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>		1
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Indomalayan islands	Sumatran Islands	Simeulue		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	1	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	6	

Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	6	
Pacific Islands	Antipodes and Chatham Islands	Chatham Island		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	8	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Trichosurus vulpecula</i>	8	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus europaeus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	8	
Pacific Islands	Bismarck Archipelago	Karkar Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Bismarck Archipelago	Lihir island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Pacific Islands	Bismarck Archipelago	Long island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Bismarck Archipelago	Manus Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Spilocuscus maculatus</i>	42	
Peramelemorphia	Peramelidae	<i>Echymipera kalubu</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus praetor</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Bismarck Archipelago	Mussau Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Spilocuscus maculatus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Bismarck Archipelago	New Britain		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Thylogale brunii</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus praetor</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Bismarck Archipelago	New Ireland		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Macropus agilis</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Thylogale brunii</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Spilocuscus maculatus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus praetor</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Easter Island	Easter Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	8	
Pacific Islands	Fiji	Gau island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	45	
Pacific Islands	Fiji	Kadavu Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	45	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	45	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	45	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	45	
Pacific Islands	Fiji	Koro Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	45	

Pacific Islands	Fiji	Taveuni Island		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	45	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	45	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	45	
Pacific Islands	Fiji	Vanua Levu		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	45	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	45	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	45	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	45	
Pacific Islands	Fiji	Viti Levu		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	45	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	45	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	45	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	45	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	45	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	45	
Pacific Islands	Hawaii	Big Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	46	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	46	
Pacific Islands	Hawaii	Kahoolawe		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	48	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	46	
Pacific Islands	Hawaii	Kauai		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	46	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus hemionus</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	48	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	46	
Pacific Islands	Hawaii	Maui		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	46	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>	46	
				Introduced to Lanai which is connected to Maui during ice ages
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Antilope cervicapra</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	46	

Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	46	Introduced to Lanai which is connected to Maui during ice ages
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Axis axis</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	46	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	46	Introduced to Moloka'i which is connected to Maui during ice ages
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	48	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	48	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	46	
Pacific Islands	Hawaii	Niihau		
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	48	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	46	
Pacific Islands	Hawaii	Oahu		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes auropunctatus</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Axis axis</i>	46	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	46	
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Petrogale penicillata</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	48	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	46	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	48	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	46	
Pacific Islands	Kosrae and Pohnpei	Kosrae		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Kosrae and Pohnpei	Pohnpei		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Louisiade Archipelago	Fergusson Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Louisiade Archipelago	Misima Island		
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Louisiade Archipelago	Rossel Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Louisiade Archipelago	Sudest Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Louisiade Archipelago	Woodlark Island		
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Maluku Islands	Buru		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverra zibetha</i>	42	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	42	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Babyrousa babyrousa</i>	42	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Maluku Islands	Gebe Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Maluku Islands	Great Kai Island		

Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	42	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Thylogale brunii</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Spilocuscus maculatus</i>	42	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura maxi</i>	42	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
<hr/>				
Pacific Islands	Maluku Islands	Halmahera		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	42	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	42	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
<hr/>				
Pacific Islands	Maluku Islands	Obira		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura monticola</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	42	
<hr/>				
Pacific Islands	Maluku Islands	Seram		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Paradoxurus</i>	42	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>hermaphroditus</i>		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	6	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
			42	Introduced to Ambon which is connected to Seram during ice ages
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	Introduced to Ambon which is connected to Seram during ice ages
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Spilocuscus maculatus</i>	42	Introduced to Ambon which is connected to Seram during ice ages
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	42	
			42	Introduced to Ambon which is connected to Seram during ice ages
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Crocidura maxi</i>	42	Introduced to Ambon which is connected to Seram during ice ages
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	42	Introduced to Ambon which is connected to Seram during ice ages
			42	Introduced to Ambon which is connected to Seram during ice ages
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>		Introduced to Ambon which is connected to Seram during ice ages
<hr/>				
Pacific Islands	Mariana Islands	Guam		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bubalus arnee</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa marianna</i>	8	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	8	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	8	
<hr/>				
Pacific Islands	Mariana Islands	Saipan		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa marianna</i>	50	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	50	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	50	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	50	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	50	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	50	
<hr/>				
Pacific Islands	Mariana Islands	Tinian		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	50	

Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	50	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	50	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	50	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	50	
Pacific Islands	Marquesas	Hiva Oa		
			52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Pacific Islands	Marquesas	Nuku Hiva		
			52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	52	Only listed by archipelago, assigned to biggest island
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	52	Only listed by archipelago, assigned to biggest island
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Pacific Islands	Marquesas	Ua Pou		
			52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	52	Source notes presence in nearly all islands in archipelago (not this one in specific)
Pacific Islands	New Caledonia	Grande Terre		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	54	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	54	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	54	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	54	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	54	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	54	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	54	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	54	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	54	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	54	

Pacific Islands	New Caledonia	Lifou Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	54	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	52	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	52	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	54	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	54	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	54	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	54	
Pacific Islands	New Caledonia	Mare Island		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	54	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	52	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	52	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	52	
Pacific Islands	New Caledonia	Ouvea Island		
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	54	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	54	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	54	
Pacific Islands	New Hebrides	Efate		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	New Hebrides	Espiritu Santo		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
			8	Only specified presence in archipelago.
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>		Assigned to biggest island
			8	Only specified presence in archipelago.
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>		Assigned to biggest island
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
			8	Only specified presence in archipelago.
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>		Assigned to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
			8	Only specified presence in archipelago.
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>		Assigned to biggest island
			8	Only specified presence in archipelago.
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>		Assigned to biggest island
Pacific Islands	New Hebrides	Nendo		
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	New Hebrides	Pentecost Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Pacific Islands	New Zealand	South Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>		
			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>		
			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela erminea</i>		
			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela nivalis</i>		
			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela putorius</i>		
			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>		
			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>		
			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Hemitragus jemlahicus</i>		
			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas

				island but they are connected during ice geas
			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Rupicapra rupicapra</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Cervus elaphus</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Cervus nippon</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Dama dama</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa timorensis</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rusa unicolor</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Macropus eugenii</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Macropus parma</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Macropus rufogriseus</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Petrogale penicillata</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Diprotodontia	Macropodidae	<i>Wallabia bicolor</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Trichosurus vulpecula</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus concolor</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>		Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas

			8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	8	Source does not specify if introductions are to south or north island but they are connected during ice geas
Pacific Islands	Niue and Tonga Islands	Niue		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	55	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	55	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	55	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	55	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	55	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	3	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	55	
Pacific Islands	Niue and Tonga Islands	Tongatapu		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	3	Only country is given. Assigned to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	3	Only country is given. Assigned to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	3	Only country is given. Assigned to biggest island
Pacific Islands	Niue and Tonga Islands	Vavau		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Pacific Islands	Palau Islands	Babelthuaap		
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	3	
Pacific Islands	Samoan Islands	Savaii		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	8	Source only list archiplegao. Here assigned to biggest island
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	8	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	8	
Pacific Islands	Samoan Islands	Tutuila		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Samoan Islands	Upolu		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Pacific Islands	Schouten Islands	Biak		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a

Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Schouten Islands	Numfor		
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Society Islands	Moorea		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
			56	Indirect evidence. Source only states presence on nearly all islands in area sand lists rat free islands (nbot including this)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	56	Indirect evidence. Source only states presence on nearly all islands in area sand lists rat free islands (nbot including this)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	56	Indirect evidence. Source only states presence on nearly all islands in area sand lists rat free islands (nbot including this)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>		
Pacific Islands	Society Islands	Raiatea		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
			56	Indirect evidence. Source only states presence on nearly all islands in area sand lists rat free islands (nbot including this)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	56	Indirect evidence. Source only states presence on nearly all islands in area sand lists rat free islands (nbot including this)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	56	Indirect evidence. Source only states presence on nearly all islands in area sand lists rat free islands (nbot including this)
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>		
Pacific Islands	Society Islands	Tahiti		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
			8	Only specified by archipelago. Assigned to biggest island
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	8	Only specified by archipelago. Assigned to biggest island
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	8	Only specified by archipelago. Assigned to biggest island
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	8	Only specified by archipelago. Assigned to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	8	Only specified by archipelago. Assigned to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	8	Only specified by archipelago. Assigned to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	8	Only specified by archipelago. Assigned to biggest island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	8	Only specified by archipelago. Assigned to biggest island
Pacific Islands	Solomon islands	Bougainville Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus praetor</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Solomon islands	Guadalcanal		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus praetor</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands	Solomon islands	Malaita		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a

Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands Solomon islands New Georgia				
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands Solomon islands Pavuvu Island				
			42	Only stated introduced to Russell islands but Pavuvu Island is by far the largest of these
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	Only stated introduced to Russell islands but Pavuvu Island is by far the largest of these
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	Only stated introduced to Russell islands but Pavuvu Island is by far the largest of these
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>		Only stated introduced to Russell islands but Pavuvu Island is by far the largest of these
Pacific Islands Solomon islands Rennell Island				
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Pacific Islands Solomon islands San Cristobal				
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	42	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Pacific Islands Solomon islands Tetepare Island				
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	58	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	58	
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	58	
			58	Not assigned to species in source but this is the most widespread species in the region
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus exulans</i>		
Pacific Islands Solomon islands Vella Lavella				
Diprotodontia	Phalangeridae	<i>Phalanger orientalis</i>	42	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	42	
Renmaining Islands Aleutian Islands Amchitka Island				
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	59	
Renmaining Islands Aleutian Islands Atka Island				
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Vulpes lagopus</i>	59	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	59	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	59	
Renmaining Islands Aleutian Islands Attu Island				
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	59	
Renmaining Islands Aleutian Islands Bering Island				
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	60	
Rodentia	Cricetidae	<i>Myodes rutilus</i>	61	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	61	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	61	
California Channel				
Renmaining Islands Islands San Clemente				
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	62	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	62	
California Channel				
Renmaining Islands Islands Santa Catalina				
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	62	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Antilope cervicapra</i>	62	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bison bison</i>	62	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus hemionus</i>	62	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	62	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	62	
Renmaining Islands Chiloe Archipelago Guafo Island				
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	63	
Renmaining Islands Crozet Islands Ile de l'Est				
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	68	
Renmaining Islands Crozet Islands Possession island				

Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	68	
Renmaining Islands	Falkland Islands	East Falkland Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
			65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Lycalopex griseus</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Cetartiodactyla	Camelidae	<i>Lama guanicoe</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus europaeus</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Sylvilagus floridanus</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	65	Source do not divide between East and West Falkland Island
Renmaining Islands	Galapagos	Floreana Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	66	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	66	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	66	
Renmaining Islands	Galapagos	Isla Isabella		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	66	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	66	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	66	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	66	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	66	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	66	
Renmaining Islands	Galapagos	Isla San Cristobal		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	66	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	66	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Bos primigenius</i>	66	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	66	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	66	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	66	
Renmaining Islands	Galapagos	Isla Santa Cruz		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	66	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	66	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	66	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	66	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus africanus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	66	
Renmaining Islands	Galapagos	Santiago Island		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	66	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	66	
Renmaining Islands	Gulf of California Islands	Isla Angel de la Guarda		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	25	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	25	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	25	
Renmaining Islands	Gulf of California Islands	Isla Carmen		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	25	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	25	

Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis canadensis</i>	25	
Renmaining Islands	Gulf of California Islands	Isla Cerralvo		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	25	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	25	
Renmaining Islands	Heard and MacDonald Islands	Kerguelen		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	64	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	64	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	64	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	64	
Renmaining Islands	Islas Marias	Isla Maria Madre		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	25	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	25	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	25	
Perissodactyla	Equidae	<i>Equus ferus</i>	25	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	25	
Renmaining Islands	Kuril islands	Atlasov Island		
Rodentia	Cricetidae	<i>Microtus oeconomus</i>	68	
Renmaining Islands	Kuril islands	Iturup		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	68	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	68	
			68	Source only lists "Most of the larger islands" Here assigned to the two biggestst
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>		
Renmaining Islands	Kuril islands	Urup		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	68	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	68	
Carnivora	Carnivora	<i>Neovison vison</i>	68	
			68	Source only lists "Most of the larger islands" Here assigned to the two biggestst
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>		
Renmaining Islands	Kuril islands	Onkotan		
Rodentia	Cricetidae	<i>Microtus oeconomus</i>	68	
Renmaining Islands	Kuril islands	Shiashkotan		
Rodentia	Cricetidae	<i>Microtus oeconomus</i>	68	
Renmaining Islands	Kuril islands	Simushir		
Rodentia	Cricetidae	<i>Microtus oeconomus</i>	68	
Renmaining Islands	Marion Island	Prince Edward Islands		
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	68	
Renmaining Islands	Revillagigedos Islands	Socorro Island		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	25	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	25	
Renmaining Islands	Saint Helena	Saint Helena		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	65	
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	65	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	65	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	65	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	65	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	65	
Renmaining Islands	Sao Tome and Principe	Ilha Do Principe		
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	70	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Cercopithecus mona</i>	70	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	70	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	70	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	70	
Renmaining Islands	Sao Tome and Principe	Sao Tome		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela nivalis</i>	70	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Civettictis civetta</i>	70	
Cetartiodactyla	Suidae	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	70	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Cercopithecus mona</i>	70	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	70	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	70	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	70	
Renmaining Islands	Sea of Japan	Honshu		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
		<i>Herpestes</i>	39	
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>auropunctatus</i>		
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Mustela sibirica</i>	39	

Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Neovison vison</i>	39	
Carnivora	Procyonidae	<i>Procyon lotor</i>	39	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Paguma larvata</i>	39	
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Muntiacus reevesi</i>	39	
Eulipotyphla	Erinaceidae	<i>Erinaceus europaeus</i>	39	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	39	
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	39	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Macaca cyclopis</i>	39	
Primates	Cercopithecidae	<i>Macaca mulatta</i>	39	
Rodentia	Cricetidae	<i>Ondatra zibethicus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Echimyidae	<i>Myocastor coypus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	6	
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Callosciurus erythraeus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Sciurus vulgaris</i>	39	
Renmaining Islands	Sea of Japan	Okushiri		
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	39	
Renmaining Islands	Sea of Japan	Sado Island		
Carnivora	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	-	a
Carnivora	Mustelidae	<i>Martes melampus</i>	39	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	39	
Renmaining Islands	Socotra archipelago	Socotra		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	32	
Carnivora	Viverridae	<i>Viverricula indica</i>	32	
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	32	
Eulipotyphla	Soricidae	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	32	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	32	
Renmaining Islands	South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands	South Georgia Island		
Cetartiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	8	
Renmaining Islands	West Baja California Islands	Isla Guadalupe		
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	25	
Rodentia	Muridae	<i>Mus musculus</i>	25	

a Dogs and cats assumed present for any island with at least 10,000 people